

Is soil respiration of a chernozem under shallow cultivation similar to moldboard plowing or no-tillage?

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ABSTRACT

Herein, we report a 6-year-long investigation on the CO₂ emission (soil respiration) of a chernozem soil under conventional moldboard plowing (MP) and two conservation tillage techniques, namely shallow cultivation (SC) and no-tillage (NT). This study aims to compare soil respiration data among SC, and MP or NT treatments and investigate the underlying processes influencing the magnitude of soil-derived emissions. CO₂ fluxes were measured using static and dynamic chamber methods in seven replicates weekly during and biweekly to monthly outside growing seasons. We investigated postharvest yield and root biomass, post-tillage mulch thickness, soil water content (SWC) and temperature (Ts) via a monitoring system and portable instruments, soil chemical parameters via wet chemical analyses, and community-level physiological profiles of the soil microbial community using the MicroResp™ technique. The 6-year average soil respiration under SC (0.093 mgCO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹) was the same as the mean emission in NT. Both of these conservation treatments showed significantly elevated CO₂ emissions compared with the mean soil respiration under conventional MP (0.081 mgCO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹). We found that vegetation biomass via root respiration and denser straw residue cover could be major factors of higher CO₂ emission under SC. Additionally, the higher soil respiration in SC compared with MP could result from the high soil organic carbon (SOC) content. Similarly, elevated soil respiration in NT can occur because of the highest mean SOC and SWC as well as the densest straw residue layer among the three treatments. MicroResp™ measurements revealed differences in the substrate use efficiency of the microbial community under the three treatments, therefore suggesting that the treatment effect on CO₂ emission is caused by differences in microbial communities. Following crop production and soil respiration together, the CO₂ emission to yield ratio was the lowest under SC, similar to MP, and highest under NT treatment. The CO₂ emissions of the treatments exhibited variability over the years. Therefore, longer experimental time is essential to find more established conclusions of different tillage techniques.

1. Introduction

Understanding the governing factors of soil CO₂ emission, also known as soil respiration (Rs), is essential for developing biogeochemical models, which are necessary for predictions of future climate scenarios and important for developing mitigation strategies for greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from the agricultural sector (Hidy et al., 2022). Climate change is an urgent issue, as concentrations of GHGs in the atmosphere have been increasing since the Industrial

Revolution, causing disturbances in the global biogeochemical cycles (Canadell et al., 2021). There is a wide range of publications about the global carbon budget and the effects of anthropogenic disturbances (agricultural activities such as land use change, tillage operations, and fertilization) on soil-derived CO₂ emissions, the carbon sequestration and the global carbon cycle, including the soil carbon cycle (Post and Kwon, 2000; Xu and Shang, 2016; Francioni et al., 2019; Friedlingstein et al., 2020).

Tillage operations can alter the soil environment, including physical

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properties (compaction, aggregate stability, etc.), soil temperature (Ts), soil water content (SWC), soil chemical properties (carbon, nitrogen content, etc.), microbial biomass, community, and activity. It also contributes to plant emergence and biomass development, thereby altering Rs in the short and long term (Gelybó et al., 2022). Numerous studies have examined the effects of contrasting tillage operations, such as conventional plowing and conservation no-tillage, on soil organic carbon content (SOC) or carbon sequestration, Rs, and the relation between these parameters (Lal, 2016; Dencső et al., 2021; Gong et al., 2021; Gelybó et al., 2022; Jakab et al., 2023). However, these findings vary according to climate, soil type, and vegetation; therefore, long-term measurements of the effects of different tillage techniques on croplands are still warranted. Several studies have reported elevated Rs after conservation tillage, whereas others report contrary results (Hendrix et al., 1988; Oorts et al., 2007; Dong et al., 2017; Forte et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2022). Based on an earlier literature review by the present authors, it was found that 36 % out of the 42 highly related studies reported elevated CO₂ emissions under conventional techniques, 38 % concluded higher emissions under no-tillage, and 26 % showed no differences between the two techniques. Out of the investigated 62 experiments on soil CO₂ and N₂O emissions, only five experiments lasted more than 3 years, with most experiments (26) being studied for 2 years (Dencső, 2023). Therefore, while there are many soil respiration studies available in the literature, there are very limited numbers of long-term studies presented; hence more founded conclusions are hard to derive.

However, the former studies of the authors, along with several others in the literature, deal with the two contrasting techniques; there is a lack of knowledge about cultivation methods that can be regarded as intermediate techniques. The long-term effects of numerous conventional and conservation techniques are yet to be further examined, including techniques such as shallow cultivation, deep cultivation, disk tillage, tine tillage, and minimum or reduced tillage, in addition to plowing and no-tillage. Dencső et al. (2021) and Gelybó et al. (2022) have previously investigated the no-tillage (NT) technique, therefore, the present study assesses the shallow cultivation (SC) technique, which is considered a conservation technique and aims to compare the properties of SC with those of conventional moldboard plowing (MP) and conservation NT treatment, focusing on Rs and its major driving factors such as vegetation, soil chemical parameters, Ts, SWC, and soil microbial processes. We complemented the field study with laboratory measurements, including a straw mulch experiment, and used the MicroResp™ method to determine the community-level physiological profile of soil microbial populations to draw more well-established conclusions. The novel aim of this study is to present a long-term 6-year investigation with a robust dataset, which is rare in the scientific literature, about the effect of a non-rotary tillage method along with conventional and conservation tillage techniques on soil carbon sequestration and Rs of a chernozem type soil. For this objective, we initiated an investigation on a tillage experiment set several decades ago with consistently cultivated parcels situated in Central-East Hungary. We hypothesized that Rs under SC is closer to NT than MP because of similar soil chemical parameters. We also hypothesize that the effects of different tillage techniques should be measured for at least > 3 years to draw more established conclusions.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Site description

The Józsefmajor Experimental and Training Farm's (Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences, MATE; GAK Kft.) long-term tillage experiment was initiated by Professor Márta Birkás in 2002 (Dekemati et al., 2020). Six different tillage techniques (moldboard plowing, disking, moldboard plowing with deep loosening, deep cultivator, shallow cultivator, no-tillage) in four parcel replications were in operation on Haplic Kastanozem (Aric, Pantoloamic, Pachic, Bathycalcic; WRB) chernozem type soil. Each parcel size was 13 m × 150 m.

Crop rotation and adaptable fertilization were used in the experiment (Table 1). Cropping systems were harmonized with improved practices, including sowing and chemical treatments (suppressing weeds and pests) in two different passes only. Harvest was done by a harvester, which after chopping straw or stalks spread on the soil surface evenly. The different agro-technical operations (sowing, fertilization, tillage) were always carried out on the same day in the different treatments. The improved management was utilized uniformly for all crop types during all years.

The long-term Rs measurements started in 2013 on one parcel of SC, MP, and NT tillage treatments. Herein, we focused on the effects of conventional MP (28–30-cm cultivation depth), SC (18–20-cm cultivation depth), and NT (no-tillage operations) from 2015. MP is a conventional rotary technique, while SC is a non-rotary cultivation, and no soil disturbances occurred under NT, except seedbed preparation prior to sowing. The number of passes in tillage systems was minimized. There was no stubble management, and tillage operations were done in either September or October. The soil surface was protected by chopped straw after cereal harvest in all treatments until the tillage event. These periods were not pronounced for wide-row crops (maize, soybean) due to late harvest dates. MP was further improved by surface preparation using a packer machine in the same pass of the plowing. The quality of soil under SC did not require additional soil management following tillage. Sowing operations were also minimized. For cereals (wheat, oat) and wide-row crops (maize, soybean) seedbed preparation and sowing were done in one pass.

The climate of the experimental site is humid continental (*Dfb*, according to the Köpper climate classification) with large seasonal variations in the temperature. The mean air temperature was 12.2°C over the 6-year experimental period (2015–2020). 2015, 2018, and 2019 were slightly warmer (12.6–13.0 °C), while 2016, 2017, and 2020 were slightly colder (11.6–12.0 °C) than the long-term average. 2015 and 2018 were drier years (428 mm and 430 mm), 2017 was around average (498 mm), while 2016, 2019, and 2020 were wetter (510–561 mm) than the 6-year average precipitation (491 mm). 2016, 2019, and 2020 had higher precipitation totals (294 mm) during the growing seasons (309–382 mm), while the other growing seasons were drier than average (211–252 mm).

The soil can be characterized as a typical Central European chernozem on loess parental material, featuring a clay loam texture with over 30 % clay content in the Ap (0–30 cm), AB (30–50 cm), and Bk (50–90 cm) genetic horizons. The 2CBk layer (90–150 cm) has a sandy clay loam texture. In the soil horizon, the cation exchange capacity (CEC) decreases from 28 cmol kg⁻¹ to 14 cmol kg⁻¹ with depth, while the calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) content is 0 % in the upper layers and 25 % in 2CBk. The temperature and moisture regimes of the soil are Mesic and Ustic, respectively.

2.2. Environmental measurements

The Ts and SWC monitoring system was set up using 5TM Decagon probes (METER Group, Inc., formerly Decagon Devices, Pullman, WA, United States) at 5–10-, 15–20-, 30–35-, and 40–45-cm depths in each treatment. The probes were inserted horizontally into pre-excavated soil profiles in each treatment, and they recorded both Ts and SWC simultaneously. Measurement frequency was set to 10 minutes, and the daily average was used for the statistical analysis. The probes were removed every year prior to tillage, sowing, and harvesting, in order to protect their integrity, then reinstalled after those operations. The monitoring system was used to determine the effects of the different tillage techniques on Ts and SWC. The sample numbers (daily means) concerning the whole experimental period were n_{Ts} = 1746, 1675, 1258, and 822 and n_{SWC} = 1596, 1593, 1261, and 792 for the four investigated depths.

In environmental campaign measurements, the Ts and SWC values of the topsoil (upper 12 cm) were determined using portable instruments near the gas measurement points (seven replicates in each measurement

Table 1
Details of the experimental years.

Year	Crop	Tillage	Fertilization	Dosage (kgN ha ⁻¹)	Sowing	Harvest
2014–2015	Winter wheat	02.10.2014	07.10.2014	28.5	08.10.2014	08.09.2015
			16.04.2015	35.0		
			29.05.2015	15.0		
2016	Maize	28.10.2015	28.10.2015	42.0	18.04.2016	24.10.2016
			16.04.2016	72.0		
			27.10.2016	24.0		
2016–2017	Winter oat	28.10.2016	03.03.2017	100.0	01.11.2016	12.07.2017
			20.03.2018	60.0		
			10.10.2018	20.0		
2018 2018–2019	Winter wheat	11.09.2017 10.10.2018	11.02.2019	30.0	26.04.2018 10.10.2018	17.09.2018 18.07.2019
			02.10.2019	20.0		
			08.10.2020	60.0		
2019–2020	Winter oat	02.10.2019 08.10.2020	20.02.2020	60.0	09.10.2019	18.07.2020

day per treatment) simultaneously to Rs measurements. With this method, spatial heterogeneity was more representative, and environmental parameters could be better linked to Rs. These campaign measurements were performed using a Brannan thermometer (Brannan, United Kingdom) and the Campbell Hydrosense II SWC probe (Campbell Scientific, Logan, UT, United States) from 2019 to 2020.

2.3. Soil analysis

Soil samples were collected in triplicate regularly from the upper 0–10-cm depth for soil SOC, N_{tot}, NO₃-N, and NH₄-N analysis on each tillage treatment from 2016 to 2020. In the first year (2015) of this study, no soil samples were collected. The overall sample numbers were n_{soC} = 65, 43, 72; n_{Ntot}, NO₃, NH₄ = 114, 92, 121 for MP, SC, and NT, respectively. Winter (Dec-Feb), Spring (Mar-May), Summer (Jun-Aug), and Fall (Sep-Nov) soil chemical sampling occasions were done. In the case of SOC, the sampling was less frequent as SOC is less variable in time.

Additionally, a campaign was conducted on the vertical heterogeneity of SOC, N_{tot}, NO₃-N, and NH₄-N at depths of 0–5, 5–10, 10–15, and 15–20-cm in 2016. Sampling of SOC was done in January and March with four and three replicates, respectively. Sampling for N_{tot}, NO₃-N, and NH₄-N determination was done in February, March, April, July, and September, with three replicates in each month.

SOC and soil nitrogen measurements were based on wet chemical and gas distillation methods (the Tyurin method and the modified Kjeldhal method, ISO 11261:1995 and MSZ 20135:1999) (Jankauskas et al., 2006; Akhtar et al., 2011).

2.4. Plant production/biomass measurements

The yield and root dry weights were measured annually. Plants were measured after harvest, separating 4X-4X adaptable samples (small, mid, good, best) from treatments checking for dry biomass, length of straw or stalks, and their health status. Roots were removed from the soil by the required soil depth and area for specific plants. Roots were removed as completely as possible under field circumstances thus, sampling depths depended on the crops. After cleaning the roots, we weighed the biomass and assessed the formation of the root development. The yield was determined by measuring the weight of the harvester in accordance with industrial practice.

Additionally, we conducted a winter oat straw mulch campaign measurement after the harvest and tillage operations in 2020. We collected nine straw samples per treatment of on-surface straws with 20 × 20 cm quadrats. We collected the entire oat straw layer from the soil surface of the designated quadrats. The dry weight of these samples was measured after drying to a constant mass at 65°C.

2.5. Soil respiration measurements

We measured Rs in seven replicates for each tillage treatment using the static chamber method coupled with GC analysis (Gelybó et al., 2022) from 2015 to 2018. Subsequently, we improved the methodology using the PP System EGM5 IR-analyzer (PP Systems, Amesbury, MA, United States) based on the dynamic chamber method. The incubation time for the static chamber technique was 20 minutes, whereas the EGM analyzer's measurement time was 2 minutes; both intervals were determined based on preliminary field tests. Sampling was done weekly during the growing seasons and biweekly to monthly during off seasons. Rs was estimated from the initial and final CO₂ concentrations using linear equations (Gelybó et al., 2022), whereas the EGM analyzer calculated CO₂ fluxes in situ. Following the determination of Rs each year, we calculated CO₂ to yield indices for the three treatments. This involved upscaling the measured mean emissions annually and dividing them by the corresponding yearly yield data.

2.6. Laboratory measurements

2.6.1. The effect of residue cover on soil respiration

Laboratory experiments were performed to validate field observations. Stem residue cover is a common and essential management under conservation tillage techniques thus, we set up a laboratory experiment from the treatment with the most extensive stem residue cover (NT) after winter oat was harvested, and stem residues were left on the field in 2020. In this experiment, our aim was to investigate the stem residue effect on Rs, as we hypothesized that CO₂ emission peaks after harvest times occurred due to freshly generated residue covers under field conditions. Preparing for the Rs measurements, undisturbed soil sample cores were collected in five to seven replicates from the clear surface and residue-covered spots of the NT parcel with sampling cylinders. The diameter of the sampling cylinders was 10 cm, and the height was 20 cm, where 10 cm was for undisturbed soil height and 10 cm headspace. Each sample had its exclusive cylinder, which was sealed in the bottom after being inserted into the soil and removed. After sample collection, we brought the samples into the laboratory. There, the CO₂ emission for each sample was measured daily in the first week and then twice a week due to a decline in the emission timeline. The experiment lasted for 28 days. The residue-covered and clear-surface soil samples were kept on field SWC, and SWC was monitored daily using a scale to maintain the original moisture content, hence eliminating the influence of moisture on Rs. SWC was kept at field conditions for the first 2 weeks, following which the samples were not held at constant SWC any longer, rather they were let slowly dry out, while the measurements were continued. The chemical parameters of each column were measured after the completion of the experiment to exclude soil disturbances during CO₂ measurements. Soil samples were removed from each cylinder, and after homogenization, N_{tot} analysis was performed.

2.6.2. Microbial analysis of field samples

MicroResp™ analyses were performed over 2 years, in 2016 and 2020, based on the standard methodology (Campbell et al., 2003). The soil samples were collected from depths of 0–5, 5–10, 10–15, and 15–20-cm following the MP, SC, and NT treatments in triplicates in relatively wet soil in 2016. We uniformly set the SWC of and sieved (< 2 mm grain size) samples to $16.8\% \pm 3.0\%$. We added 15 different substrates (sugars: D-(+)-galactose [GAL], trehalose [TRE], L-(+)-arabinose [ARA], D-glucose [GLC], and D-fructose [FRU]; carboxylic acids: citric acid monohydrate [CIT], DL-malic acid [MAL], Na-succinate [SUC], and 3,4 dihydroxy benzoic acid [DHB]; and amino acids: L-alanine [ALA], L-lysine hydrochloride [LYS], L-glutamine [GLN], L-leucine [LEU], L-arginine [ARG], and L-glutamic acid [GLU]) and distilled water. For a more complex analysis, soil samples collected from a depth of 0–10-cm were tested with MicroResp™ using 23 substrates in 2020. These substrates included the following additional types: sugars (D-xylose, D-mannose, and L-rhamnose), polyols (myo-inositol, D-mannitol, and D-sorbitol), L-asparagine-monohydrate, gluconic-acid-potassium (GLA), and L-serine replacing L-leucine (amino acids), as well as distilled water (control). After 6 h of incubation at 25°C in a 96-deepwell plate, the CO₂ gas produced was detected via sensitive absorption plates. Absorbance was measured using a plate reader (Anthos 2010; Biochrom, Cambridge, UK) at 570 nm, and CO₂ emissions were inferred from the absorption findings (Renault et al., 2013). Absorption plate and CO₂ concentration calibration were performed using a GC-FID instrument (Fisons GC8000). SOC, pH(H₂O), pH(KCl), total nitrogen, ammonium, and nitrate nitrogen were determined for each sample. These measurements can differentiate the substrate use efficiency among microbial communities under specific tillage treatments, facilitating the determination of differences in activity and community of soil microbes.

2.7. Data handling

There were gaps and unrealistic values in the Ts and SWC datasets because of probe malfunctions, drying cracks in the soil, animal impacts, etc. Before analysis, we filtered and synchronized the Ts and SWC datasets from different tillage treatments for better comparison results. Ts and SWC data analysis were performed based on the daily means. Conversely, we used raw, non-averaged data for the analysis of soil chemical datasets. The filtering of Rs data was similar to a technique formerly presented by Gelybó et al. (2022). Rs data were analyzed over the entire 6-year period annually, during the growing seasons and the postharvest periods. Spearman's correlation coefficient (*r*) was used to calculate the relationship between the soils' physical and chemical characteristics and Rs in a multivariate analysis. Prior to analysis, we synchronized the datasets as data availability was not sufficient from every measurement day.

Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism Version 9.1.0. (221) for Windows software. We used D'Agostino & Pearson test to determine dataset normality, and based on those results, we used Kruskal–Wallis test with Dunn's multiple-choice test or one-way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance). Two-way ANOVA analysis was used for determining the effect of tillage and years on CO₂ emissions. Mann–Whitney *t*-test analysis was performed in the case of two-dataset comparisons (i. e., straw mulch lab experiment). The raw datasets were used for treatment comparisons, whereas the daily means were used for detecting environmental correlations. The number of point data is shown under figures and tables.

3. Results

3.1. Environmental drivers

Based on continuous monitoring measurements, there were no significant differences ($p > 0.5$) in the 6-year mean Ts of the soil under

different tillage treatments, irrespective of the investigated soil layers (Fig. 1a). Conversely, SWC differed significantly among the treatments ($p < 0.005$). SWC in the 5–10-, 15–20-, and 40–45-cm soil layers under SC was the lowest among the tillage treatments ($p < 0.005$). SWC was the highest in the three upper layers under NT, whereas it was the highest at 40–45 cm under MP ($p < 0.005$; Fig. 1b).

3.2. Soil chemical properties

The mean SOC content of the soil was higher under SC compared with that under MP ($p < 0.005$) and lower compared with that under NT ($p < 0.005$, Fig. 2a). There were similar findings for the N_{tot} content ($p < 0.005$, Fig. 2b). Because of the similar trends of these two parameters, the C:N ratios of the soil under MP, SC, and NT treatments were similar at 9.4, 9.3, and 9.4, respectively. The 5-year mean NO₃-N content was significantly higher under NT than MP ($p < 0.005$), while this parameter was not different under SC compared to any other treatments ($p > 0.005$, Fig. 2c). Elevated mean NH₄-N content was determined under the conservation treatments than under MP ($p < 0.005$, Fig. 2d).

Vertical soil chemical parameters showed differences in SC. This trend in heterogeneity was also reported in the case of NT. Under SC, only the SOC content in the upper layer was significantly higher compared with that in the lowest layer ($p < 0.05$), whereas it differed in almost all the layers under NT ($p < 0.05$). No soil layers under MP showed differences in SOC content ($p > 0.5$, Fig. 3a). The N_{tot} content under SC showed differences only between the 0–5- and 15–20-cm layers ($p < 0.005$), whereas all the layers showed different N_{tot} contents under NT ($p < 0.05$). The N_{tot} content under MP was vertically homogenous ($p > 0.5$, Fig. 3b). No significant differences were found in soil NO₃-N and NH₄-N content of different soil layers (Fig. 3c and d).

3.3. Plant production/biomass measurements

After harvest and tillage operations, the weight of on-surface oat straw mulch under SC was intermediate among the treatments, with significant differences observed only between MP and NT ($p < 0.005$, Fig. 4).

Yield and root biomass were measured yearly after harvest in each treatment. Annual yields were the highest under SC in 2016, 2018, 2019, and 2020, corresponding partly to dry root weights, which were the highest in 2016, 2018, and 2020 (Table 2).

3.4. Soil respiration

Weekly Rs measurements exhibited a specific trend during the experimental years. Rs demonstrated a temporal variation that mainly followed the seasonal course of the Ts of the tillage technique. During fall-sown crop years, Rs declined before soil temperature decreased because of the effect of the vegetation. As the crops approached harvest, crop activity and root respiration decreased, which led to a declining trend in the total Rs. After the harvest, elevations in Rs were observed in 2017 and 2019, and this could be attributed to crop residues (Figure S1).

According to cumulative CO₂ curves, there were distinguished dates when the emissions under the conservation techniques (SC or NT) increased greatly compared to MP in relatively short periods. In 2015, the emissions of the two conservation tillage methods elevated significantly compared to MP during the mid-growing season. In 2016 and 2018, maize and soybean had the most significant effect among other crops on the emissions under the conservation treatments, with major elevations in the emission curves during mid-growing seasons. In 2017 and 2019, winter oat and winter wheat did not substantially affect the emissions among treatments. In contrast to 2017, elevated emissions started under conservation tillage systems after the harvest of winter oats in 2020 (Fig. 5).

The 6-year mean Rs (2015–2020) under SC was significantly higher compared with that under MP ($p < 0.005$) and did not differ from that

Fig. 1. (a) 6-year mean (all data) soil temperature (Ts) and (b) soil water content (SWC) of moldboard plowing (MP), shallow cultivation (SC), and no-tillage (NT) treatments at 5–10-, 15–20-, 30–35-, and 40–45-cm depths during the investigation time; $n_{Ts} = 1746, 1675, 1258, \text{ and } 822$ and $n_{SWC} = 1596, 1593, 1261, \text{ and } 792$ in 5–10-, 15–20-, 30–35-, and 40–45-cm depths, respectively. Lowercase letters indicate significant differences among tillage systems ($p < 0.05$). “x” indicates mean values and horizontal lines indicate the median for the 6-year sampling period.

Fig. 2. (a) 5 year mean (all data) soil organic carbon (SOC), (b) total nitrogen (N_{tot}), (c) NO_3 -N and (d) NH_4 -N content of the 0–10-cm soil layer under moldboard plowing (MP), shallow cultivation (SC), and no-tillage (NT) treatments; $n_{SOC} = 65, 43, \text{ and } 72$; $n_{N_{tot}}, NO_3, NH_4} = 114, 92, \text{ and } 121$ in MP, SC, and NT, respectively. Lowercase letters indicate significant differences among the tillage systems ($p < 0.05$). “x” indicates mean values and horizontal lines indicate the median for the 5-year sampling period.

under NT ($p > 0.5$, Fig. 6).

The differences in the annual Rs of the investigated tillage treatments were significant in 2016, 2018, and 2020 (Table S1). In 6 years, we found the same trend in the treatment effect during the growing seasons.

In the case of SC, elevated annual mean Rs were observed in 2016 and 2020 (the two wettest years of the whole experimental period) compared to the 6-year average emission. In the other treatments, there was no data from specific years that deviated from the result of the 6-

Fig. 3. Mean values of campaign sampling on vertical heterogeneity from January to September 2016. Vertical heterogeneity of (a) SOC, (b) N_{tot} , (c) NO_3-N and (d) NH_4-N in the upper 0–20-cm layer (0–5-, 5–10-, 10–15-, 15–20-cm resolution) under moldboard plowing (MP), shallow cultivation (SC), and no-tillage (NT) treatments; $n_{SOC} = 7, 7,$ and 7 and $n_{N_{tot}, NO_3, NH_4} = 14, 14,$ and 15 under MP, SC, and NT, respectively. Lowercase letters indicate significant differences among soil depths of a tillage system ($p < 0.05$). “x” indicates mean values, and horizontal lines indicate the median for the campaign period.

Fig. 4. Winter oat straw weight based on a campaign measurement after harvest and tillage under moldboard plowing (MP), shallow cultivation (SC), and no-tillage (NT), $n = 9$ (20×20 cm quadrat) for each treatment. Lowercase letters indicate significant differences among the tillage systems ($p < 0.05$). “x” indicates mean values and horizontal lines indicate the median.

year period. The lowest annual emissions under all three treatments occurred in 2019 (Table S1).

The two-way factorial analysis indicated that significant differences can be detected regarding the tillage ($p < 0.0001$) and regarding the year ($p < 0.0001$), however, the tillage \times year interactions were not significant ($p > 0.05$; Table 3).

Table 2

Vegetation parameters after harvest concerning experimental parcels (the highest values are underlined). Yields: parcel results provided by a harvester, root: results provided by averages of small, intermediate, large and best species of each treatment, annual $n_{yield} = 1,$ $n_{root} = 4$ per treatment.

Parameter	Mean yields ($t\ ha^{-1}$)			Mean root weights ($t\ ha^{-1}$)		
	MP	SC	NT	MP	SC	NT
Treatments						
2015 (winter wheat)	5.70	5.77	4.82	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
2016 (maize)	8.41	<u>9.03</u>	8.25	8.23	<u>8.31</u>	6.54
2017 (winter oat)	<u>6.25</u>	4.90	4.46	<u>3.42</u>	<u>2.86</u>	2.92
2018 (soybean)	0.87	<u>1.30</u>	0.66	<u>5.08</u>	<u>5.72</u>	4.52
2019 (winter wheat)	4.79	<u>5.90</u>	3.87	<u>2.34</u>	2.29	1.94
2020 (winter oat)	7.34	<u>8.78</u>	7.75	2.30	<u>3.89</u>	3.33

3.5. Multivariate dependence of soil respiration on environmental and chemical parameters

During the environmental campaign measurement (2019–2020), the highest apparent T_s dependency (based on the exponential model) of R_s occurred under SC. The connection between T_s and R_s was stronger in the postharvest periods, irrespective of the growing seasons (Fig. 7).

Statistical analysis showed significant correlations between R_s and T_s in each treatment ($p < 0.05$). However, we were unable to detect the SWC dependence of R_s under field conditions with the method we used ($p > 0.5$, Fig. 8).

We also analyzed the dependence of R_s on T_s , SWC, SOC, N_{tot} , NH_4-N , and NO_3-N contents from a multivariate point of view. Among these

Fig. 5. Cumulative CO₂ emissions (based on mgCO₂ m⁻² s⁻¹ effluxes) under moldboard plowing (MP), shallow cultivation (SC), and no-tillage (NT) in each year. Yellow boxes indicate the growing seasons, and black arrows indicate the date when CO₂ curves diverge from each other. Lowercase letters indicate significant differences among the tillage systems (*p* < 0.05) in the Spring-Summer and the Summer-Fall periods.

Fig. 6. Mean CO₂ emissions under moldboard plowing (MP), shallow cultivation (SC), and no-tillage (NT) for the 6-year experimental period. Lowercase letters indicate significant differences among the tillage systems (*p* < 0.05).

variables, Rs was the most dependent on Ts (*r* = 0.41), NO₃-N (*r* = 0.47), SOC (*r* = 0.36), and N_{tot} (*r* = 0.34) with moderate correlations. Weak correlations were determined between Rs and SWC (*r* = 0.24) and NH₄-N (*r* = 0.18, Table 4).

3.6. CO₂-GHG to yield ratio

We examined the yield and CO₂ measurements under the three tillage treatments yearly. From these parameters, a CO₂-GHG to yield ratio can be calculated. Higher indices pose potential risks in climate-smart agriculture. The CO₂ emission-to-yield ratio was similar

Table 3

Two-way factorial analysis of soil respiration.

Year	Mean CO ₂ emission (mg m ⁻² s ⁻¹) regardless of tillage treatment
2020	0.111 ± 0.091 ^a
2016	0.096 ± 0.069 ^b
2015	0.091 ± 0.086 ^b
2018	0.086 ± 0.063 ^{bc}
2017	0.075 ± 0.055 ^{cd}
2019	0.073 ± 0.067 ^d
Tillage	Mean CO ₂ emission (mg m ⁻² s ⁻¹) regardless of years
NT	0.093 ± 0.078 ^a
SC	0.093 ± 0.071 ^a
MP	0.081 ± 0.063 ^b
Year	Mean CO ₂ emission (mg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)
× tillage	
Year × tillage	0.089 ± 0.071 n.s.

between SC and MP, and their indices were more favorable than that under the NT treatment. The greatest difference between tillage treatments was examined in 2018, when soybean was sown (Fig. 9).

3.7. Laboratory measurements

3.7.1. Crop residue as soil respiration enhancer

To find the effect of straw mulch – which is an essential part of conservation agriculture – on CO₂ emissions, we set up a laboratory experiment using the best-covered and most heterogeneous conservation treatment (NT). Under field conditions, higher peaks in CO₂ emissions can be examined right after harvest, which may have originated from freshly spread straw mulch. With this experiment, we intended to test this phenomenon in a controlled environment. This experiment aims to help better understand the complex environmental system responsible for higher Rs under NT treatment. We maintained and monitored the same level of SWC during the experiment in order to eliminate the SWC effect. At the end of the experiment, we determined the N_{tot} content

Fig. 7. Correlations between soil respiration and soil temperature under moldboard plowing (MP), shallow cultivation (SC), no-tillage (NT) during the whole environmental campaign period (2019–2020); (black x), the growing seasons (green dots), and the after-harvest periods (brown dots), n = 60, 51, 60 for the whole period in MP, SC, NT, respectively.

Fig. 8. Correlation of soil respiration with soil water content under moldboard plowing (MP), shallow cultivation (SC), and no-tillage (NT) during the whole environmental campaign period (2019–2020), n = 28, 27, and 27 in MP, SC, and NT, respectively.

of the soil columns. There were no significant and major differences in the SWC and N_{tot} content under the two treatments ($p > 0.5$; Fig. 10a and Fig. 10b). However, the Rs of the mulch-covered NT samples were significantly higher ($p < 0.005$) compared with that of the clear-surface NT treatment (Fig. 10c).

Table 4

Multivariate analysis of soil respiration (Rs), soil temperature (Ts), soil water content (SWC), soil organic carbon (SOC), total nitrogen (N_{tot}), nitrate nitrogen (NO₃-N), and ammonium nitrogen (NH₄-N) based on Spearman's correlation. n = 23.

p/r-values	CO ₂	SOC	N _{tot}	Ts	SWC	NH ₄ -N	NO ₃ -N
CO ₂		0.36	0.34	0.41	0.24	0.18	0.47
SOC	0.0892		0.9	-0.16	0.27	0.05	0.32
N _{tot}	0.1087	0.00***		0.03	0.21	0.12	0.34
Ts	0.0505	0.4752	0.8961		-0.1	-0.03	0.43
SWC	0.2635	0.2202	0.3392	0.665		-0.18	0.03
NH ₄ -N	0.4118	0.8306	0.5921	0.9001	0.4184		-0.16
NO ₃ -N	0.0239*	0.1419	0.1165	0.041*	0.8966	0.4545	

3.7.2. Microbial respiration experiment

MicroResp™ measurement findings can also explain Rs results. Basic chemical analysis was conducted before the experiment, and there were differences in the soil chemical parameters under the three tillage treatments at four depths, similar to the results from field conditions (Table S2).

Significant differences were found in glucose utilization and

Fig. 9. Yearly CO₂ emission to annual yield ratio under moldboard plowing (MP), shallow cultivation (SC), and no-tillage (NT) during the whole investigation time.

Fig. 10. (a) Soil water content under clear-surface no-tillage soil (NT clear) and oat straw residue-covered no-tillage soil (NT covered) (n = 60 and 105, respectively), (b) total nitrogen (N_{tot}) content (n = 5 and 7 for NT clear and NT covered, respectively), (c) soil respiration (n = 57 and 79, respectively). Lowercase letters indicate significant differences between clear and residue-covered soil (p < 0.05). “x” indicates mean values, and horizontal lines indicate the median.

cumulative substrate-induced respiration (SIR) of soils depending on sampling depth in SC and NT plots, and the SIR decreased by depth (Fig. 11a, d). However, there was no difference in the activities of microbial communities in soil samples collected from different depths in the plowed plots. No seasonal effects were detected in the 0–10 cm soil layers, and similar trends were observed in the samples collected in 2016 and 2020 (Fig. 11b, c, e, and f). Higher glucose and total SIR values were measured in SC and NT, in the 0–5-cm soil layer, however, these differences were not statistically verifiable (Fig. 11a, d). SIR values

tended to be lower in these treatments in the lower depths (10–15 and 15–20 cm) compared to MP. Although no significant differences were found between tillage treatments, glucose SIR and total SIR were the lowest in the plowed plots in the 0–10-cm soil layer (Fig. 11b, e).

4. Discussion

A previous article from the same study site reported elevated Rs under NT compared with that under MP, highlighting the importance of

Fig. 11. Glucose utilization and cumulative substrate-induced respiration (SIR) of microbial communities under different tillage treatments according to MicroResp™ measurements in 2016 (a, b, d, and e) and 2020 (c and f) sampling years; MP: moldboard plowing, SC: shallow cultivation, NT: no-tillage; 0–5, 5–10, 10–15, and 15–20 cm sampling depths, and the color darkens with the depth of sampling. b, e (2016) and c, f (2020) show the glucose utilization and cumulative substrate-induced respiration at 0–10 cm of soil samples; n₂₀₁₆ = 13 × 4/treatment; n₂₀₂₀ = 5/treatment. Lowercase letters indicate significant differences among soil depths of a tillage system for a) and d), and significant differences among tillage systems for b), c), e), f) (p < 0.05).

SOC under contrasting tillage treatments (Gelybó et al., 2022). Herein, some soil parameters (e.g., SWC) under SC were closer to those under MP than to those under NT, whereas some (SOC, residue cover) were between the values measured under MP and NT. However, Rs under SC was rather similar to that under NT than MP. Therefore, these findings suggest that different processes partly cause the similarity in Rs under SC and NT.

4.1. Effect of environmental parameters on soil respiration

Rs was mainly governed by Ts regardless of the tillage treatment, where the strongest connection could be observed in SC. It is important to note that these correlations were apparent responses; the modifier effect of the vegetation was included and was not distinguished (Han et al., 2014). Ts correlations were stronger in the postharvest period than during the growing season, indicating the effect of vegetation on Rs response. We could not detect significant SWC dependency of Rs based on the field measurements. According to the literature, Ts is the major, and SWC is the secondary governing factor of Rs in time where Ts exhibits an overriding effect (Saiz et al., 2006; Hursh et al., 2017). This may explain why we did not find an SWC correlation in time, but this does not mean that SWC is not an explanatory factor of Rs. Rs depends on SWC, and the correlation is often quadratic/parabolic according to the experimental scale (Moyano et al., 2013). In our experiment, SC treatment had the lowest SWC in the upper soil layer, but in deeper depths, it was similar to NT. It is unlikely that similar mean Rs occurred under the highest (NT) and the lowest (SC) surface SWC. Thus, in the case of SC, SWC might not be a significant explanation for the mean emission, while excess moisture may support microbial respiration in NT. Applying different tillage systems results in various outcomes under different climatic conditions. Conservation practices tend to reduce the rate of Rs in drier, arid climates and sandy soils (Abdalla et al., 2016), while their impact can be debated in more organic soils under humid climates. In warm and relatively wet conditions, conservation practices like no-tillage positively affect carbon sequestration, whereas in cooler and drier regions, its beneficial impact is less significant (Ogle et al., 2019). The climatic conditions and soil type of the present field trial amplified the effect of different tillage systems.

4.2. Implications of crops and stem residue cover

Vegetation is also an important factor of Rs via root respiration (Zhao and Shi, 2017). We found the highest annual yields under SC in 2016, 2018, and 2020, which may explain the higher Rs compared with MP in general and during those years. Following several studies, yield can correlate with root abundance and respiration (Wang et al., 2014a, 2014b; Postic et al., 2019; Liang et al., 2021; Macdonald et al., 2021), making yield a useful indicator in such experiments. The dry root weight data also support the Rs findings, as SC had the highest maize, soybean, and winter oat root weight in 2016, 2018, and 2020, respectively. In those years, the treatment effect was the most pronounced. The treatment effect was significant, especially when the summer crops were sown (2016, 2018), a phenomenon confirmed by a similar experiment (Bilandžija et al., 2016). In the case of NT, yield and root weight were not explanatory factors of the elevated Rs, owing to the fact that these parameters were smaller compared with the values examined in the MP and SC treatments. The influence of vegetation on the long-term regulation of Rs is a significant factor, while the distribution of crops also exerts an influence on the spatial heterogeneity of emissions (Han et al., 2007).

Stem residues can also elevate Rs regardless of the tillage system due to the additional supply of mineralizable carbon sources and changes in the soil environment (Tenesaca and Al-Kaisi, 2015). Stem residue cover is an important element of conservation treatments, especially of NT. While residues shall be turned into the soil under MP systems, the residue cover is more permanent under NT. The lowest stem residue cover

was in the MP treatment, whereas it was higher in conservation tillage, especially in NT. This could contribute to the elevated Rs of NT by better preserving the already highest mean SWC under this treatment. Higher SWC due to residue cover can accelerate microbial activity and influence microbial community structure, thereby increasing CO₂ emissions (Chen et al., 2017; Akhtar et al., 2019; Fu et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2021; Li et al., 2022). Although SWC was low in SC, the denser residue layer positively affects T_s as well, which can also contribute to higher Rs. Following the laboratory experiment, Rs was higher under residue-covered NT samples than under clear-surface NT despite the same moisture and N_{tot} content, highlighting that straw residues regulate emissions not only via SWC but also through other factors (e.g., its microbial respiration), consistent with the results of a previous study (Kuntz et al., 2016). With this experiment, we were able to support the hypothesis that elevated Rs can occur after harvest due to stem residues, and it can be a partial explanation of the higher mean emissions under conservation systems.

In our experiment, the lowest CO₂ to yield ratios occurred under the SC. In this conservation treatment, elevated SOC sequestration was observed in the topsoil, while higher yield might compensate for higher CO₂ emission (due to a more active soil environment) compared to MP. Crop yields were the lowest in NT every year, and the CO₂-to-yield ratio was unfavorable in this trial. No-tillage can reduce global warming potential by inhibiting CO₂ and other GHG emissions, especially for acid and alkaline soils under dry climates. In parallel with that, no-tillage can also significantly increase yields of crops like barley, maize, rice, and soybean under such conditions (Naujokienė et al. 2018; Li et al., 2023). Our present case study highlights the importance of the benefits of no-tillage can be reduced, and other conservation methods should be investigated, like the non-rotary shallow cultivation. In addition to soil type and climate, crop diversification can positively influence GHG emissions and yield relation (greenhouse gas intensity) under reduced or no-tillage systems (Babu et al., 2023).

4.3. The role of soil organic carbon and nitrogen contents

A couple of years after the setup of Józsefmajor's long-term tillage experiment, there were differences in the SOC content of the conventional and conservation tillage treatments (Huisz et al., 2006). Our data showed that the mean SOC value under SC was between the two other contrasting treatments, but the emissions were higher in both conservation treatments than in MP. Carbon and nitrogen accumulation of soil under SC and NT were major in the upper 10-cm layer, and in the deeper layers, the treatment effect was more blurred. Additionally, the trend of SOC (MP ≤ SK ≤ NT) was similar to the trend of Rs during the post-harvest period, especially in certain years, such as 2019 or 2020, suggesting that SOC can be a reason for elevated Rs in SC and NT. A study from the experimental site reported similar SOC trends among the treatments, both in the stable and labile fractions of SOC (Jakab et al., 2023). A moderate correlation can be found between Rs and SOC (Anokye et al., 2021), while stronger connections can also be expected (Sun et al., 2015). SOC content is spatially heterogeneous and dependent on several factors (SWC, microbial biomass) thus, correlations on arable fields can be difficult to detect. SOC and N_{tot} accumulation under conservation tillage treatments can be due to the extent straw residue layer on the surface, which supports carbon and nutrient supply into upper soil layers (Dalal et al., 2011; Carvalho et al., 2017; Haas et al., 2022). Several studies confirm that elevated Rs can occur because of carbon sequestration in the topsoil (Hendrix et al., 1988; Lognoul et al., 2017; Gong et al., 2021). In the topsoil (0–10 cm) under SC, higher carbon sequestration occurred compared with data observed under MP, where the soil was highly aerated and drier. It is important to note that in lower depths, SWC under SC is similar to the SWC under NT. Conversely, the upper soil layer under NT exhibited elevated carbon sequestration but was significantly wetter and presumably less aerated. Overall, the SOC content in the upper 10 cm was the lowest under MP, medium under SC, and the highest under NT. In lower depths (15–20 cm), there were no

differences in the SOC contents of the soil under the different tillage methods. Soil carbon and nitrogen cycles are closely related to each other. A moderate dependence of Rs on NO₃-N was determined in this experiment. Similarly to Rs, NO₃-N is more variable in time than SOC and N_{tot}. It has an annual variation related to fertilization (Huang et al., 2017), which can explain the higher correlation between soil emission and NO₃-N. Sosulski et al. (2020) also reported a positive and comparable correlation to those of our results between Rs and NO₃-N due to the contributing effect of mineral fertilization on soil autotrophic (root respiration) and heterotrophic (microbial activity) emissions. Important to note that the dosage of mineral fertilization is a key factor in this topic. Pareja-Sánchez et al. (2019) also reported the elevating effect of higher nitrogen fertilization on Rs, especially in the case of no-tillage treatments, due to higher above-ground biomass, thus elevated heterotrophic respiration. The article also noted the role of nitrogen availability on carbon mineralization, emphasizing that the relationship is still uncertain in some regards. In contrast to the abovementioned results, Li et al. (2015) found that higher mineral fertilization above a certain dosage can even lead to lower CO₂ emissions.

4.4. Effect of microbial differences

Soil nutrient availability with elevated SWC can be a key factor of the microbial community of soils (Tong et al., 2021). Higher SOC under conservation tillage systems can provide a substrate for microorganisms, thereby increasing soil life, soil health, thus heterotrophic respiration. Soil microbial biomass, activity, and community structure can differ between conventional and conservation tillage treatments (Badagliacca et al., 2018; Bösch et al., 2022). Soil microbial respiration and microbial biomass, including SIR, can be used to assess land use and soil management practices for soil quality and health (Winding et al., 2005; Onica et al., 2018). MicroResp™ measurements at the Józsefmajor site demonstrated that the glucose-induced and cumulative SIR differed between plowed plots and soil conservation treatments, suggesting that microbial community composition or enzyme activity affects Rs differently. The SIR by soil depth indicates plowing mixes and homogenizes the different soil layers. Microbial factors under field conditions are highly variable over time, making it challenging to monitor the effect of treatment on the soil microbiome (Melero et al., 2011; Tatti et al., 2015). The SIR in this long-term field experiment revealed a similar pattern in two different years. The SIR method is most widely used to estimate soil microbial biomass. Higher glucose utilization can indicate higher microbial biomass in SC and NT soil samples at 0–10 cm. Furthermore, the higher SWC and SOC in NT compared with MP may favor microbial activity, resulting in elevated CO₂ emissions, although no apparent correlation between soil respiration and SWC was evidenced in this study.

5. Conclusions

The 6-year mean Rs under the non-rotary SC was the same as that under NT, both elevated compared with that under conventional MP, owing to elevated SOC, N_{tot}, and on-surface straw residue layer in these conservation systems. The highest vegetation biomass under SC can also contribute to elevated Rs via root respiration, the elevated Rs under NT can be attributed to the highest SOC of the topsoil, and the highest SWC may also be an important facilitator through microbial activity. The cumulative CO₂ emission curves demonstrated that the impact of the tillage treatments was notable throughout the crop development phase and beyond harvest. The CO₂-to-yield ratio was the most favorable under SC treatment. This study concludes that no-tillage has benefits in some soil parameters and may have advantages with limits in climate-smart agriculture, although other conservation techniques like non-rotary shallow cultivation can also be a possible solution for sustainability in temperate climatic conditions on chernozem soils. These results, based on a 6-year investigation, highlight the importance of

experimental time, as the treatment effect was minor in some years.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Balla István: Resources. **Szili-Kovács Tibor:** Methodology, Data curation. **Tóth Eszter:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Dencső Márton:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Bakacsi Zsófia:** Writing – review & editing. **Ágota Horel:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Takács Tünde:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Birkás Márta:** Resources. **Füzy Anna:** Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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